

Metal Chelate Complexes of Schiff's Base derived from Salicylhydrazide and Diacetyl

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Sacconi¹ reported the nickel (II) chelates of the condensation products of aliphatic dicarboxy dihydrazides with salicylaldehyde, ortho-hydroxy-naphthaldehyde, ortho-amino-benzaldehyde etc.

The present paper reports the metal chelates of the condensation product of salicylhydrazide and diacetyl.

Salicylhydrazide condenses with diacetyl on refluxing the components in alcoholic medium to give a product of the Schiff's base type which, as its elemental analyses show, conforms to the composition $C_{18}H_{18}O_4N_4$. As in the case of the condensation product of diacetyl and carboxylic acid hydrazide², this compound may also be represented by the structure (I) which is capable of existing in the tautomeric form (II) as well :

The study of the metallic chelates of this ligand reveals that in forming the complexes, it reacts in the tautomeric 'enol' form.

The metallic complexes were obtained by heating on waterbath a mixture of alcoholic solutions of the metal acetate (1 mole) and a solution of the ligand (1 mole) in aqueous ammonia till the smell of ammonia subsided. The metallic chelates were precipitated as highly coloured amorphous products, insoluble in water, slightly soluble in hot alcohol and benzene, but easily soluble in chloroform. They are also soluble in dilute alkali solutions on warming, when ammonia is evolved. Complex salts of bivalent metallic ions like Cu(II),

1. L. Sacconi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1326.
2. L. Sacconi, *Z. anorg.-allgem. Chem.*, 1954, **275**, 249.

Ni(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) of this ligand have been prepared, but those of cobaltous, manganous and uranyl ions could not be isolated in the pure state. This is probably due to the very condition of preparation *viz.*, the ammoniacal medium which prevented their formations. All the metallic complexes isolated correspond to the empirical formula $ML_2 \cdot 2NH_3$, where LH_2 represents a molecule of the ligand and M Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II); but the determination of the molecular weights of the metallic chelates by elevation of boiling points of the chloroform solutions point to their dimeric formula. They are therefore, represented by the following structure(III), the ligand exhibiting bidentate function :

III

where M = Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II). The deep brown copper(II) compound with a magnetic moment 1.84 B.M. is most probably a true penetration complex with dsp^2 hybrid bands. The orange-red nickel(II) complex is diamagnetic and is probably planar with dsp^2 hybrid bands. Zinc(II) and cadmium(II) form deep yellow diamagnetic complexes as expected.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Schiff's base : To a hot alcoholic solution of salicylhydrazide (0.1 mole) was added diacetyl (0.05 mole) and the mixture was refluxed on the water bath for 2 hr. It was allowed to cool to room temperature and the product collected on a filter, washed with alcohol and then dried.

The base which chars above 195° , is insoluble in water, slightly soluble in alcohol, but is completely soluble in aqueous ammonia giving an yellow solution. Anal. Found : N, 15.74%. Calculated for $C_{18}H_{19}O_4N_4$: N, 15.82%.

Metal complexes of salicylhydrazide diacetyl : To a suspension of the Schiff's base (0.05 mole) in alcohol, aqueous ammonia was added dropwise with stirring until a clear yellow solution was obtained. To this yellow solution was added a solution of metal acetate (0.05 mole) in aqueous ammonia. The mixture was heated on waterbath, till the excess of ammonia was boiled off from the solution. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and the precipitated compound was filtered, washed with water and alcohol and then dried in a desiccator.

TABLE 1
Analytical data

Composition	Found (%)		Calculated (%)		Magnetic moment in B.M. (30°)
	Nitrogen	Metal	Nitrogen	Metal	
$C_{18}H_{16}O_4N_4Cu \cdot 2NH_3$ (deep brown)	18.48	14.42	18.69	14.13	1.84
$C_{18}H_{16}O_4N_4Ni \cdot 2NH_3$ (orange red)	19.05	12.63	18.89	12.90	Diamagnetic
$C_{18}H_{16}O_4N_4Zn \cdot 2NH_3$ (yellow)	18.41	14.28	18.61	14.49	„
$C_{18}H_{16}O_4N_4Cd \cdot 2NH_3$ (deep yellow)	16.65	22.88	16.86	22.55	„

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Received March 7, 1969.